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EFFECTIVENESS OF THE FORMATION OF TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS
IN FREESTYLE WRESTLERS AT THE TRAINING STAGE

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'quv-mashq bosqichidagi erkin kurashchilarni jismoniy, texnik-taktik tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan haftalik sikllarni qo'llash hamda zamonaviy uskunalardan foydalanib bajariladigan maxsus mashqlar majmuasini qo'llash hamda uni samaradorligini aniqlash to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Erkin kurash, mezosikl, metodika, haftalik sikl, maxsus mashqlar majmuasi, texnik-taktik, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, musobaqa, mashg'ulot jarayoni.

Annotation. This article provides information on the application of weekly cycles aimed at developing the physical, technical, and tactical training of freestyle wrestlers at the training stage, as well as the application of a complex of special exercises performed using modern equipment and determining its effectiveness.

Keywords: Freestyle wrestling, mesocycle, methodology, weekly cycle, complex of special exercises, technical-tactical, physical training, competition, training process.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о применении еженедельных циклов, направленных на развитие физической, технической и тактической подготовленности борцов вольного стиля на этапе подготовки, а также о применении комплекса специальных упражнений, выполняемых с использованием современного оборудования и определении его эффективности.

Ключевые слова: Вольная борьба, мезоцикл, методика, недельный цикл, комплекс специальных упражнений, технико-тактическая, физическая подготовка, соревнование, тренировочный процесс.

Relevance. Today, wrestling is distinguished not only among Olympic sports, but also on a global scale by its popularity, competitiveness, and the need for a high level of technical and tactical training from athletes. From this point of view, the formation of technical and tactical skills in athletes at the training stage is one of the urgent scientific and practical problems not only in national, but also in international sports science. According to the International Wrestling Federation (UWW), as a result of technical and tactical updates in 2020-2024, the activities of wrestlers are increasingly based on the effective use of speed, combination actions, and counterattacks. At the same time, based on foreign experience, such countries as Japan, the USA, Iran, and Russia have implemented step-by-step, digitalized, and video-analytical approaches to technical and tactical skills in the training of young athletes. This indicates that the emphasis only on physical training is outdated; now the athlete's knowledge of when, how, and in what variant to apply each technical movement is considered an important factor.

The purpose of the research is to develop proposals and recommendations for improving the technical and tactical training of freestyle wrestlers.

Research objectives. Determination of technical and tactical indicators of freestyle wrestlers;

Development of a methodology for improving the technical and tactical training of freestyle wrestlers.

Research results and their discussion. The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that situational, analytical, and innovative methods of technical and tactical training of wrestlers at the training stage have not yet been sufficiently implemented in the sports system of Uzbekistan.

Practical training in most cases is based only on repetitive methods. Therefore, scientific research on this topic serves the creation of theoretical foundations and practical models, the development of methodological manuals for coaches, and the competitiveness of Uzbek kurash wrestlers in the international arena. In freestyle wrestling, technical-tactical training is the athlete's ability to correctly, effectively, and thoroughly execute wrestling actions (technique), apply them appropriately to the opponent at the right time and place (tactics), make decisions during combat, choose strategies, and build combinations. Technical training is the development of skills for correct, safe, and effective execution of wrestling actions and techniques. This includes, among other things, basic wrestling techniques, standing up (podsechka), lifting by the waist, turning, rotating, and counter-attacks (kontrpriemy). Parter technique involves wrestling in a lying position, throwing the opponent backward, and knocking them down. The technical and tactical training of freestyle wrestlers directly determines the results they achieve in sports. Although technical skills require a strong physical base, tactical decisions depend on the athlete's intellect, experience, and ability to understand the struggle. Therefore, by practicing technique and tactics in a coordinated, consistent, and planned manner, the athlete prepares for high competitions. As a result, the optimal development of the technical and tactical training of freestyle wrestlers is achieved.

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